

1 Liquid chromatography (ion mobility) coupled to organic and inorganic mass
2 spectrometry for determination of chiral thyroid hormones in human milk

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37 **Abstract**

38 Human Milk (HM) contains essential trace elements crucial for infant development, with iodine
39 playing a key role during pregnancy and lactation. Thyroid hormones (TH) are the only
40 biologically active iodine-containing compounds, but their chiral forms had not been quantified
41 in HM due to the lack of analytical methods. A three-phase hollow-fiber liquid-phase
42 microextraction (HF-LPME) method was developed to extract eight TH from HM, followed by
43 separation using a UHPLC column-switching system combining chiral and reversed phases.
44 Detection was performed using quadrupole time-of-flight (QTOF) and inductively coupled
45 plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). The methods are sensitive, reliable, and reproducible,
46 allowing quantification of TH, including chiral forms, at natural levels. Additionally, ion mobility
47 mass spectrometry (IMMS) provided drift times and collision cross-section (CCS) parameters.
48 The concentrations of TH in 30 HM samples were reported.

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51 **Keywords:** *Hollow-fiber liquid-phase microextraction; ion mobility; ultra-high-performance*
52 *liquid chromatography; iodine speciation; quadrupole time of flight; thyroid hormones; human*
53 *milk.*

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75 1 Introduction

76 The elemental composition constitutes up to 0.5% of human milk (HM) (Truchet &
77 Honvo-Houéto, 2017), nevertheless, the role of iodine among other elements in influencing the
78 infant's health has been extensively reported (Dorea, 2002; Dror & Allen, 2018; Rayman, 2000).
79 Iodine is required to produce thyroid hormones (THs), which are essential for infant growth and
80 neurological development during the first 2 years of life (Rohner et al., 2014; Zoeller & Rovet,
81 2004). Moreover, infants are the age group most sensitive to iodine deficiency because they
82 have the highest iodine requirements relative to body weight and only small amounts of stored
83 intrathyroidal iodine (Etling et al., 1986). Iodine deficiency can affect carbohydrate metabolism,
84 oxygen consumption, protein synthesis and immune system (Reinhardt et al., 1998; Robinson et
85 al., 1998) and in HM, maternal iodine deficiency impact on the HM metabolome (Z.-M. Li et al.,
86 2020). TH have chiral centers and their enantiomers present different biological and therapeutic
87 effects (Eisdorfer & Post, 1967; Millan-Alanis et al., 2021). Likewise, the levels of D-thyroxine (D-
88 T₄) do not have any influence on the metabolic rate, but on the contrary, the levels of L-thyroxine
89 (L-T₄) do clearly influence it (Scanu et al., 1969). However, D-T₄ influences the levels of lipogenic
90 enzymes in the liver, decreases the secretion of thyrotropin (TSH) and both, D-T₄ and D-
91 triiodothyronine (D-T₃) reduces cholesterol levels (Gübitz & Juffmann, 1987). Moreover, D-T₄ is
92 mainly used as anticholesterolemic agent, while L-T₃ and L-T₄ are the natural thyroid hormones,
93 which are responsible for the basic metabolism. For this reason, L-T₄ is used as replacement
94 therapy in hypothyroidism (Scanu et al., 1969). The therapeutic use of both isomers needs
95 optical purity to avoid negative cardiac side effects (Wainer, 1993).

96 The enantiomers of THs are known to have quite different pharmacological effects. In
97 contrast to L-T₄, D-T₄ shows no basic metabolic rate enhancement but was shown to alter levels
98 of lipogenic enzymes in the liver and to reduce serum cholesterol significantly, acting by
99 increasing the rate of degradation and oxidation of cholesterol (Goglia, 2005; Hulbert, 2000;
100 Lopez et al., 2007; Ness & Lopez, 1995). In addition, suppression of thyroid stimulating hormone
101 (TSH) excretion caused by D-T₄ has been observed (Cunningham et al., 1998). Besides, studies
102 have shown that the biological effectiveness of D-T₃ is markedly less than that of L-T₃,
103 corresponding to 5–30% of the activity of L-T₃ (Jackson-Hayes et al., 2003; Oppenheimer et al.,
104 1991).

105 The research of the last years has identified several iodothyronines other than T₃ and T₄
106 that display some thyromimetic activities. Among them, T₂ assumed great interest as it mimics
107 several effects of T₃ on energy metabolism (Horst et al., 1989; O'Reilly & Murphy, 1992) without
108 inducing thyrotoxic effects (Cimmino et al., 1996). A single dose of diiodothyronine (T₂) (25
109 µg/100 g body weight) stimulated the resting metabolic rate (RMR) of hypothyroid rats and
110 increased the liver oxidative capacity to the same extent as the same dose of T₃ (Lanni et al.,
111 1992). Moreover, T₂ significantly reduced serum triglyceride and cholesterol levels and
112 increased liver oxygen consumption (Lanni et al., 2005).

113 Several analytical methods have been previously developed to determine THs in human
114 serum (HS). Likewise, T₂, T₃, T₄, reversed T₃ (RT₃), monoiodotyrosine (MIT) and diiodotyrosine
115 (DIT) have been determined by hollow fiber-liquid phase microextraction (HF-LPME) combined
116 with capillary electrophoresis (CE) and ultraviolet detection (UV) (P. Li et al., 2014). A method
117 based on a protease treatment followed by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)
118 coupled to inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) was developed for iodide,
119 T₄, DIT, MIT and RT₃, using the heteroatom iodine as a "tag" in the atomic detector (Michalke et
120 al., 2000). A CE-ICP-MS method was used for iodine, iodate, T₄ and T₃ in urine and HS samples
121 after dilution (Michalke & Schramel, 1999). TH (T₄, T₂, T₃, RT₃, MIT, DIT, thyronine (T₀) and
122 tyrosine (Tyr)) have also been determined in HS, urine and tissues by HPLC coupled with
123 photodiode-array detection (Chatzimichalakis et al., 2004), while 3-iodothyronine (T₁), T₂, T₃,

124 RT₃, T₄ were determined by isotope dilution HPLC-MS and electrochemiluminescent
125 immunoassay (ECLIA) (Kunisue et al., 2011). In HM, T₄, T₃ and RT₃ have been determined by solid
126 phase extraction (SPE) followed by LC-MS/MS (Z.-M. Li et al., 2020), while thyroid-stimulating
127 hormone (TSH) and T₄ were determined by monoclonal antibodies and a thyroxine-specific
128 antibody labelled with a ruthenium complex, respectively (Vass et al., 2022). T₄ and T₃ have also
129 been determined by radioimmunoassay (RIA) in plasma (Van Wassenaeer et al., 2002) and HM
130 (Mizuta et al., 1983; Van Wassenaeer et al., 2002).

131 Due to the therapeutic use of T₃ and T₄ stereoisomers, there are many methods for their
132 chiral recognition in pharmaceuticals (Koidl et al., 2006; J. Lee et al., 2022; M. K. Lee et al., 2008;
133 Y. Lee et al., 2021; Millan-Alanis et al., 2021). The T₄ stereoisomers have also been determined
134 in HS by SPE followed by HPLC-UV (Wang et al., 2003). However, under our best of knowledge
135 there is a lack of an analytical method for chiral THs determination in HS including
136 simultaneously other THs and, under our knowledge, they have not ever been quantified in HM.

137 Herein, a novel analytical method was developed for eight THs in HM, including chiral
138 forms, combining HF-LPME and separation into an HPLC column switching system. The feasibility
139 of using ICP-MS detection, using iodine in the THs as a “tag” was examined and compared with
140 organic mass spectrometry using quadrupole time-of-flight (QTOF) tandem mass spectrometry.
141 Both methodologies were also complemented by ion mobility mass spectrometry (IMMS). HF-
142 LPME is a reliable, and simple method of low cost that implies low sample consumption, allows
143 fiber disposability, which in turn avoids sample cross-contamination, making it a promising
144 technique for extracting THs in HM. The parameters of quality were comparable using QTOF or
145 ICP-MS as detectors, but the QTOF also allowed for determining THs without iodine (T₀). IMMS
146 enabled the separation of TH providing their drift times (DTs) and collision cross section (CCS)
147 parameters. As proof of concept, the analytical method was applied to 30 HM samples.

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149 2 Materials and methods

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151 2.1 Chemicals and reagent solutions

152 Ultrapure water, employed for the preparation of all aqueous solutions, was procured
153 from a Milli-Q system (Millipore Milli-Q, Watford, UK). Ammonium acetate, glacial acetic acid,
154 formic acid, phosphoric acid, CaCl₂, propylthiouracil, sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS), ascorbic
155 acid, citric acid, dithiothreitol, 1-octanol, anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and the standards L-T₄, D-T₄, RT₃, T₂,
156 DIT, MIT, T₀ and ¹³C₆-L-T₄ (internal standard) were purchased from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany),
157 while T₃ was from MP Biomedicals (Irvin, CA, USA), ammonia and Na₂CO₃ were from Quality
158 Chemicals (Badalona, Barcelona, Spain), and methanol, acetonitrile and acetone optima grade
159 for LC/MS were purchased from Fisher Scientific (Waltham, MA, USA).

160 Pure standards were dissolved in a 10 mM NaOH in a 1:1 (v/v) mixture of methanol:water
161 (ultrapure) and subsequently stored at -20 °C. Calibration standard solutions (1–75 µg L⁻¹ of MIT,
162 DIT and T₀; 10–250 µg L⁻¹ of T₂; 10–750 µg L⁻¹ of T₃, RT₃, D-T₄ and L-T₄ and 100 µg L⁻¹ of internal
163 standard) were prepared from individual stock solutions by diluting them with 0.05 M
164 CH₃COONH₄ in a 60:40 (v/v) mixture of ultrapure water:acetonitrile and the pH was set at 4.5
165 with CH₃COOH for SPE extraction, and diluting them with 50 mM Na₂CO₃ for HF-LPME.

166

167 2.2 Sample collection and preparation

168 Thirty HM samples were collected during the first 4 months of infancy and subsequently
169 stored at -80 °C until analysis. HM samples were collected during 2023 at the University Hospital

170 Germans Trias I Pujol, Badalona, Spain. A Local Ethics Committee approved the study and written
171 informed consent was obtained from all participating women (Ethics Committee Reference: PI-
172 23-042). Comprehensive oral and written information regarding the study was provided to all
173 participants. Women with multiple gestations, diseases, or perinatal complications were
174 excluded from the study. The exclusion criteria encompassed women who were unable to
175 breastfeed due to severe symptomatology requiring intensive care unit support, women who
176 required the use of medications with potential adverse effects on the infant, and those for whom
177 obtaining HM was not feasible.

178

179 2.3 Three-phase hollow fiber liquid phase microextraction of human milk thyroid hormones

180 The sample preparation method was adapted and optimized for HM starting from a
181 previously published method for HS (P. Li et al., 2014). The optimized sample preparation
182 procedure is shown in **Figure S1**. The process contains two clean-up processes: liquid-liquid-
183 extraction (LLE) for protein and lipid elimination, and HF-LPME for extraction and
184 preconcentration. A total volume of 500 μL of HM was mixed with 500 μL of acetone and 62.5
185 μL of an antioxidant mixture containing 25 g L^{-1} citric acid, ascorbic acid and dithiothreitol (DTT)
186 in ultrapure water. The mixture was centrifuged after mixing and equilibrating for 30 minutes.
187 The procedure was repeated twice by mixing the supernatant with 250 μL of a 1:1 (v/v) mixture
188 of ultrapure water:acetone. After dilution up to 25 mL with ultrapure water, 150 μL 0.1 mM of
189 sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) were added as an ion pair reagent, and the pH was set to 2.8
190 with H_3PO_4 . After the sample clean-up by LLE, TH were extracted and preconcentrated by HF-
191 LPME using three phase mode. Hollow fibers Accurel Q3/2 polypropylene (600 μm inner
192 diameter x 200 μm wall thickness x 0.2 μm pore size) were used (3M Deutschland GmbH Öhder
193 Straße, Wuppertal, Germany). To this end, the fibers were cut into 4.5 cm pieces and later
194 cleaned into an ultrasound bath with acetone for 5 min. The clean air-dried fiber was immersed
195 in 1-octanol for 25 seconds to facilitate the formation of the supported liquid membrane (SLM).
196 The acceptor phase (20 μL of 50 mM Na_2CO_3) was injected into one syringe and the two ends of
197 the clean air-dried fiber were connected to two syringes and submerged into the donor phase
198 (the previous cleaned-up HM sample obtained by LLE). Thus, the analytes were extracted from
199 HM to 1-octanol and then to the Na_2CO_3 solution. The HF-LPME was performed for 15 minutes
200 at 1250 rpm. The extraction temperature was 20 $^\circ\text{C}$. The extracts were collected and analyzed
201 by UHPLC-QTOF, HPLC-ICP-MS and IMMS.

202

203 2.4 UHPLC-QTOF conditions

204 Quantification of TH was performed using an Agilent Technologies 6550 iFunnel Q-TOF
205 LC/MS tandem mass spectrometry system coupled to an Agilent 1290 Infinity II LC system. The
206 injection volume was 20 μL . Data acquisition and analysis were performed using Agilent
207 MassHunter Workstation software. The separations of TH were carried out using a column-
208 switching system, which combined a reversed-phase column (KromaPhase, C18,
209 Octadecylsililica, 5 μm particle size x 150 mm length x 4.6 mm inner diameter, Scharlab,
210 Barcelona, Spain) and a chiral column (Chiralpak QN-AX, O-9-(tert-butylcarbamoyl) based on
211 quinine immobilized on silica gel (5 μm particle size x 150 mm length x 4.6 mm inner diameter,
212 Daicel, Osaka, Japan).

213 The mobile phases used in the UHPLC method were ultrapure water (A) and acetonitrile
214 (MeCN, B) each containing 0.05 M ammonium acetate and pH 4.5 with acetic acid. The column
215 temperature was set at 30 $^\circ\text{C}$. In position 1 of the column switching valve, the injected HM extract
216 passes through the reversed-phase column and then to the QTOF, while in position 2, the sample
217 passes for the chiral column also before the detector. The following gradient procedure was
218 applied: Position 1: 5% B remained for 3 min, increased linearly to 20% B in 1 min and kept for 5

219 min, ramped to 40% B gradually in 1 min and kept for 5 min, then increased to 80% B in 1 min.
220 Position 2: 80% B kept for 17 min. Position 1: finally returned to initial conditions in 1 min and
221 re-equilibration during 3 min. The reference masses m/z 121.0509 and 922.0098, were
222 constantly introduced into the system for mass correction

223 Targeted MS/MS mode was recorded in the 50–800 m/z range. Other parameters were
224 set as follows: capillary voltage (3500 V), drying gas flow rate (13 L min^{-1}), temperature ($200 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$),
225 gas nebulizer pressure (35 psi), sheath gas ($350 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and flow rate (11 L min^{-1}). The fragmentor
226 voltage was adjusted at 175 V, nitrogen was used as collision gas and voltages were in the range
227 of 14–24 V for the fragmentation of compounds. Data were acquired with a scan rate of 0.9
228 spectrum/second at centroid mode. **Table S1** shows the MS/MS parameters for TH detection.

229

230 2.5 HPLC-ICP-MS conditions

231 The analysis was carried out in a triple quadrupole ICP-MS model 8800 (Agilent
232 Technologies) using collision gas (helium) at a flow rate of 4.5 mL min^{-1} . A mixture of H_2 (2 mL
233 min^{-1}) and O_2 (40%) was used in the MS/MS mode for iodine ($127 \rightarrow 143$). A tuning aqueous
234 solution of Li, Co, Y, and Tl at $1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ was used to tune the ICP-MS. The calibration standard
235 solutions containing TH were used to prepare internal calibration curves. Other operational
236 parameters for ICP-MS, such as sampling depth, RF forward power, carrier gas flow rate, or type
237 of nebulizer, are detailed in **Table S2**.

238

239 2.6 IMMS conditions

240 The IMMS (an Agilent Technologies 6560 Ion Mobility LC/Q-TOF coupled to an Agilent
241 1290 Infinity II LC system) conditions were similar to those described for the UHPLC-QTOF. The
242 differences were the following: MS mode was recorded in the range of 100–1700 m/z ; the
243 parameters IM Transient Rate (18 IM transient/frame), Max Drift Time (60.02 ms), Trap Fill Time
244 (20 ms) and Trap Release Time (0.15 ms) were selected for IM conditions; and the Multiplexing
245 was disabled.

246

247 2.7 Validation of the methodologies based on HF-LPME followed by UHPLC-QTOF or HPLC- 248 ICP-MS

249 To evaluate the practical reliability of the extraction method, the following figures of
250 merit were determined, namely: linearity, limit of detection (LOD), limit of quantification (LOQ),
251 repeatability (intra-day) and reproducibility (inter-day). The linearity was obtained by plotting
252 calibration curves of the relative area (analyte peak area/internal standard peak area) versus the
253 concentration of each analyte. The analytical curves were constructed first at ten levels from 1
254 to $1000 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of all TH using both UHPLC-QTOF and HPLC-ICP-MS. LODs and LOQs were
255 calculated as $a + 3S_{y/x}$ and $a + 10S_{y/x}$, respectively, where “ a ” is the origin ordinate and “ $S_{y/x}$ ” is
256 the random error in the slope and intercept values. After reshaping the calibration function, the
257 concentrations at the detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) limits were obtained. TH
258 standard solution at 1 mgL^{-1} each was measured ten times ($n = 10$) for the repeatability (intra-
259 day) and reproducibility (inter-day). UHPLC-QTOF was finally selected as the methodology for
260 the analysis of samples based on the first validation study. Thus, another calibration with eight
261 levels was performed by UHPLC-QTOF at the following concentration ranges: $1\text{--}75 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for MIT,
262 DIT and T_0 ; $10\text{--}250 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for T_2 ; $10\text{--}750 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for T_3 , RT_3 , $D\text{--}T_4$ and $L\text{--}T_4$. Additionally, a pool of
263 spiked samples was used. Thus, a volume of $500 \mu\text{L}$ of the HM pool spiked with the commercial
264 standards at different concentrations were mixed and $50 \mu\text{L}$ of the final extract was analyzed.

265

266 3 Results and discussion

267 3.1 Ion mobility mass spectrometry for thyroid hormones in human milk

268 IMMS was used as another tool for the unequivocal identification of the THs using the
269 DTs and CCS, which are unique for each one of them. A standard solution of analytes was
270 measured by IM coupled to QTOF. **Table 1** shows the DT and CCS experimentally obtained, and
271 those results were compared with databases (ccsbase.net, mcleanresearchgroup.shinyapps.io,
272 brcwebportal.cos.ncsu.edu), and **Figure 1** corresponds to a two-dimension spectrum where it
273 can be seen a mass spectrum at X-axis and a DTs spectrum at Y-axis. **Figure 1** also shows two
274 insets: Inset A highlights the separation of the position isomers T₃ and RT₃, while inset B shows
275 no separation between D and L-T₄. The separation was possible in 5 minutes. However, the
276 separation of the stereoisomers (D and L-T₄) was not possible as they have the same DT and CCS;
277 otherwise, the position isomers and the other TH were separated successfully. In addition, the
278 quantification of TH was not possible by using IMMS as it is a qualitative technique.

279 **Table 1.** Drift times and cross-collision sections values of thyroid hormones obtained
280 experimentally by IMMS.

Thyroid Hormone	Drift Time (ms)	Cross Collision Section (CCS) (Å ²)
MIT	18.9	156.7
DIT	20.7	169.4
T ₀	21.2	175.1
T ₂	24.2	195.5
T ₃	25.6	207.0
RT ₃	26.3	267.6
D-T ₄	26.6	214.3
L-T ₄	26.6	214.3

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282

283 **Figure 1.** 2D Spectrum of TH using IMMS. (A) Separation of T_3 and RT_3 in DT spectrum and (B) no
 284 separation of stereoisomers of thyroxine.

285 **3.2 Optimization of the column switching system combining chiral and reversed phase**
 286 **columns coupled to UHPLC-QTOF and HPLC-ICP-MS**

287 Initially, only the chiral column was used, but the separation of the TH was not possible
 288 and only the chiral forms of T_4 were completely resolved. The separation of T_3 stereoisomers
 289 was not possible due to the absence of a commercial standard and the limitation of the authors
 290 for their synthesis. Then, using the reversed phase, the THs were separated, but not the chiral
 291 forms of T_4 . Then the chromatographic separation of THs was carried out using a six-ways valve
 292 connected to both columns with chiral and reversed phase stationary phases and then to the
 293 UHPLC-QTOF or HPLC-ICP-MS. As can be seen in **Figure 2**, the optimized gradient by increasing
 294 the proportion of the apolar mobile phase allowed the separation of eight TH in 37 minutes.
 295 MIT, DIT, T_0 , T_2 , T_3 and RT_3 were separated in 17 minutes with the reversed-phase column and
 296 then, the column switching valve changed to position 2 to separate T_4 into D- T_4 and L- T_4 with
 297 the chiral phase column. After that, the TH were detected in the QTOF system by tandem mass
 298 spectrometry or into the ICP-MS using the iodine of the molecule as a “tag” in the atomic
 299 detector (**Figure 3**). As shown in **Figure 3A**, changing the column-switching system to position 2
 300 in 16 minutes, as previously optimized for the UHPLC-QTOF, led to the elution of RT_3 besides T_4
 301 into the chiral column. The reason is the short delay in the HPLC-ICP-MS system due to the path
 302 length from the HPLC to the detector, conditioned by the nebulizer, torch and plasma. When
 303 the position changed at 17 minutes, the T_4 eluted from the reverse phase and it was detected in
 304 the ICP-MS without chiral separation. Then, the position changes at the column switching valve
 305 was set at 16 min. As shown in **Figure 3A**, the detection of T_0 was impossible in the ICP-MS
 306 because this TH does not contain iodine.

307

308 **Figure 2.** Superimposed chromatographic gradient and UHPLC-QTOF chromatogram showing
 309 the separation of MIT, DIT and T₀ standards at 200 µgL⁻¹ and T₃, RT₃, D-T₄ and L-T₄ at 2 mgL⁻¹.

310

311 **Figure 3.** Chromatograms showing the separation of TH standards, at 1 mgL⁻¹ by (A) HPLC-ICP-
 312 MS and (B) UHPLC-QTOF. The insets of Figure B show the magnified sections of the
 313 chromatogram for better visualization of T₃, RT₃, D-T₄ and L-T₄.

314 The limits of detection and the relative standard deviation (%RSD intra- and interday) of
 315 both methodologies are shown in **Table 2**. As can be seen, the sensitivity, selectivity,
 316 reproducibility and repeatability were comparable using the UHPLC-QTOF or HPLC-ICP-MS as
 317 detector. However, the former allows determining T₀ that does not contain iodine. For this
 318 reason, UHPLC-QTOF was selected for further experiments.

319 **Table 2.** Limits of detection and quantification, repeatability and reproducibility for thyroid
 320 hormones using UHPLC-QTOF and HPLC-ICP-MS.

Thyroid Hormones		MIT	DIT	T ₀	T ₂	T ₃	RT ₃	D-T ₄	L-T ₄
UHPLC-QTOF	LOD ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	0.7	1.5	1.5	5.6	6.6	2.9	19.8	10.7
	LOQ ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	2.3	5.0	5.0	18.6	22.1	9.5	65.9	35.5
	%RSD intraday (n=10)	8	4	7	5	9	6	8	5
	%RSD interday (n=10)	9	5	7	9	9	9	9	6
HPLC-ICP-MS	LOD ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	4.1	4.2	N.D.	4.5	5.7	2.7	7.0	7.6
	LOQ ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	13.6	14.0	N.D.	14.9	19.0	9.1	23.5	25.5
	%RSD intraday (n=10)	7	8	N.D.	5	6	8	9	8
	%RSD interday (n=10)	8	9	N.D.	6	7	9	9	9

321 LOD: limit of detection; LOQ: limit of quantification; N.D.: not detectable.

322 3.3 Optimization of the three-phase-HF-LPME general configuration.

323 A pretreatment procedure was optimized prior to HF-LPME due to the complexity of the
 324 HM samples besides the possibility of oxidation of TH during the sample treatment procedures
 325 and their common binding to proteins. The antioxidant mixture used was ascorbic acid, citric
 326 acid and dithiothreitol, whereas acetone was added for the leaching of TH, as used by other
 327 authors for HS (P. Li et al., 2014). The volumes of HM samples and those reagents were carefully
 328 optimized for the minimum amount to miniaturize the method, which is important for biological
 329 samples. Thus, 500 μL of HM was enough to detect the TH in the QTOF and ICP-MS due to their
 330 sensitivity, against 2 mL used for HS (P. Li et al., 2014). After this pretreatment, SDS was added
 331 as an ion pair reagent and the variables of the HF-LPME were optimized. For the optimization of
 332 the HF-LPME method, the UHPLC-QTOF was used. An aqueous acceptor phase is
 333 recommendable due to the structure of the TH and the compatibility with the HPLC technique.
 334 However, the extraction of TH by HF-LPME using an aqueous acceptor phase was not possible
 335 because it is mixed with the donor phase (HM sample). Therefore, the HF-LPME for TH was
 336 configured in the three-phase mode using 1-octanol immobilized in the HF pores, thus providing
 337 a supported liquid membrane (SLM). The HF was cut into 4.5 cm segments, and they were fixed
 338 on the end needles of two commercial 1 mL microsyringes (U-shape configuration) as in a
 339 method previously described for TH in HS that also use HF-LPME (Z.-M. Li et al., 2020). An
 340 univariate optimization was carried out by varying one parameter as maintained constant the
 341 others using the following conditions: Na_2CO_3 30 mmol L^{-1} for donor phase, pH 3, no addition of
 342 salt for ionic strength, 20 min of extraction, 1000 rpm and 20 $^\circ\text{C}$. Each parameter was varied in
 343 4 levels and each level was analyzed in triplicate (n=3). The acceptor phase and the SLM selected
 344 were Na_2CO_3 and 1-octanol, respectively, as used in a previously described method for TH in HM
 345 based on SPE (Z.-M. Li et al., 2020). The concentration of acceptor phase varied from 30 to 60
 346 mmol L^{-1} and the optimum was 50 mmol L^{-1} (**Figure 4A**). The pH varied from 2.3 to 3.8 using H_3PO_4
 347 and the optimum was found at 2.8 (**Figure 4B**), while the ionic strength varied from not salt
 348 addition to saturation with Na_2SO_4 and the optimum was not adding salt (**Figure 4C**). The
 349 extraction time was optimized from 2 to 20 minutes (**Figure 4D**) and the optimum was 15
 350 minutes, while the temperature was optimized from 20 to 40 $^\circ\text{C}$ (**Figure 4E**) and the optimum,
 351 as a compromise was 20 $^\circ\text{C}$. Finally, the stirring speed was optimized from 750 to 1250 rpm
 352 (**Figure 4F**) and the optimum value was 1250.

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354

355

356 **Figure 4.** Optimization of the following parameters of HF-LPME: (A) Concentration of acceptor
357 phase, (B) pH, (C) ionic strength, (D) time of extraction, (E) agitation speed and (F) temperature
358 of extraction.

359

360 3.4 Validation of HF-LPME followed by UHPLC-QTOF

361 To evaluate the applicability of the proposed HF-LPME, figures of merit were determined
362 and compared with the method described in the literature based in SPE and HPLC-MS (Z.-M. Li
363 et al., 2020).

364 HF-LPME improved considerably the SPE method (Z.-M. Li et al., 2020). First, SPE is a
365 time-consuming method since it is based on a LLE in three steps and two of them are repeated
366 three times, while HF-LPME involves only one step, which is repeated three. Furthermore, SPE
367 has a drying step using the speed vacuum and then the resuspension of samples, which is not
368 required in HF-LPME. Thus, SPE usually needs more than one day compromising the stability of
369 the samples, while with HF-LPME can be analyzed on the same day of the extraction. In addition,
370 SPE is a volume-consuming technique that requires 2 mL of HM while TH can be extracted from
371 0.5 mL of HM by HF-LPME. **Figure 5** shows a typical chromatogram of TH in HM obtained by HF-
372 LPME followed by UHPLC-QTOF.

373

374 **Figure 5.** Typical chromatogram of thyroid hormones in human milk obtained by HF-LPME
 375 followed by UHPLC-QTOF in MS/MS mode (extracted ion chromatogram).

376 Once the HF-LPME followed by UHPLC-QTOF method was optimized an exhaustive
 377 validation was performed with a pool of spiked HM samples as described in the Materials and
 378 Methods section (**Table 3**).

379 **Table 3.** Validation parameters of the proposed method (HF-LPME).

Thyroid Hormones	MIT	DIT	T ₀	T ₂	T ₃	RT ₃	D-T ₄	L-T ₄
LOD (µg L ⁻¹)	0.7	1.5	1.5	5.6	6.6	2.9	19.8	10.7
LOQ (µg L ⁻¹)	2.3	5.0	5.0	18.6	22.1	9.5	65.9	35.5
%RSD intraday								
Spike 1 (n=3)	<1	<1	3	<1	<1	2	1	<1
Spike 2 (n=3)	2	2	4	<1	1	<1	6	6
Spike 3 (n=3)	6	4	5	<1	4	<1	4	3
%RSD interday								
Spike 1 (n=3)	8	6	5	4	8	7	9	9
Spike 2 (n=3)	8	10	7	7	7	6	8	7
Recovery (%) (n=3)	95	91	83	113	114	112	86	92
EF (%) (n=3)	30	41	45	26	28	52	27	32
Linearity								
a	-1955.9	928.6	674.0	5840	-834	1387.2	-484.8	123.7
b	2101.5	1281	1040.3	437.3	56.2	186.8	28.8	55.2
R ²	0.9995	0.9996	0.9996	0.9993	0.9991	0.9993	0.9996	0.9993
Range (µg L ⁻¹)	2.3 - 75	5 - 75	5 - 75	18.6 - 250	22.1 - 750	9.5 - 750	65.9 - 750	35.5 - 750
Average concentration (µg L ⁻¹ ± SEM)	13.7 ± 5.6	15.5 ± 2.1	14.0 ± 2.6	37.4 ± 5.8	51.8 ± 10.3	65.0 ± 12.9	135.3 ± 4.7	94.0 ± 16.9

380 LOD: limit of detection; LOQ: limit of quantification; For the RSD, the spiked HM samples were the
 381 following: Spike 1: 5 µg L⁻¹ of MIT, DIT and T₀; 50 µg L⁻¹ of T₂, T₃, RT₃, D-T₄ and L-T₄; spike 2: 10 µg L⁻¹ of MIT,
 382 DIT and T₀; 100 µg L⁻¹ of T₂, T₃, RT₃, D-T₄ and L-T₄; and spike 3: 50 µg L⁻¹ of MIT, DIT and T₀; 200 µg L⁻¹ of T₂;
 383 500 µg L⁻¹ of T₃, RT₃, D-T₄ and L-T₄; EF: enrichment factor; a: y-intercept; b: slope; R²: determination
 384 coefficient; SEM: standard error of mean. Validation parameters in LLE according to literature (P. Li et al.,
 385 2014)

386

387

388 3.5 Application to human milk samples

389 As proof of concept, 30 samples of HM were determined by HF-LPME followed by
 390 UHPLC-QTOF (**Table 4**). Among the 30 samples, only 5 showed all TH above their LOQ, including
 391 T₄ stereoisomers. The order of abundance of the TH was variable but mostly was as follows: D-
 392 T₄>L-T₄>RT₃>T₃>T₂>DIT>T₀>MIT. It is important to highlight that the concentration of D-T₄ was
 393 always higher than the concentration of L-T₄, and the same happened between RT₃ and T₃
 394 respectively. Furthermore, the levels of T₄ were higher than T₃ levels. Other THs were variable
 395 depending on the samples (MIT usually was the lowest TH). L-T₄ and D-T₄ have not been
 396 previously determined in HM samples, neither DIT nor T₀.

397 **Table 4.** Concentration of THs in 30 HM samples by HF-LPME followed by UHPLC-QTOF, then
 398 previously reported data of THs analyzed by other authors using different methods and samples.

Concentration ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) of THs in HM (n=30 samples)								
Thyroid hormone	MIT	DIT	T ₀	T ₂	T ₃	RT ₃	D-T ₄	L-T ₄
Minimum	2.4	5	5.6	20.2	32.1	21.3	115.1	47.9
Maximum	62	24.8	34.4	96.5	109	179.7	157.5	193.6
Mean (this work)	13.7	15.5	14.0	37.4	51.8	65	135.3	94
Standard Error of Mean	5.6	2.1	2.6	5.8	10.3	12.9	4.7	16.9
Mean (other authors) [ref]								
(Karimova et al., 1983; Mizuta et al., 1983; Salakhova et al., 1980)								
Samples: Human Milk	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	0.3-7.4	N.R.	32-499 (D+L)	
Methodologies: CPBA								
(Z.-M. Li et al., 2020)								
Samples: Human Milk	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	<LOD	0.1±0.03	0.02±0.01	0.6±0.2 (D+L)	
Methodology: LC-MS/MS								
(Bode et al., 1978; Etling & Gehin-Fouque, 1984; Jansson et al., 1983; Sack et al., 1979; Slebodziński et al., 1986; Van								
	6-20	N.R.	N.R.	N.D.	0.1-3.9	0.06-0.1	0.6-31 (D+L)	

Wassenaer et al., 2002; Vass et al., 2022)								
Samples: Human Milk								
Methodology: RIA								
(Vass et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2013)								
Samples: Human Milk	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.D.	0.4±0.2	N.R.	29.6-4076.5 (D+L)	
Methodology: Chemiluminescence								
(P. Li et al., 2014)								
Samples: Human Serum	N.D.	N.D.	N.R.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	99.2-104.9 (D+L)	
Methodology: IP- HF-LLLME-CE-UV								
(Michalke et al., 2000; Michalke & Schramel, 1999)								
Samples: Human Serum	1.1- 3.8	0-3.3	N.R.	N.R.	3.2-7.5	2.4-5.2	45-78 (D+L)	
Methodology: ICP- MS								
(Kunisue et al., 2011)								
Samples: Human Serum	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	1.4±0.5	N.R.	83.8±16	
Methodology: ECLIA								
(Kunisue et al., 2011)								
Samples: Human Serum	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	1.4±0.6	N.R.	74.9±17	
Methodology: LC- MS/MS								
(Wang et al., 2003)								
Samples: Human Serum	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	130- 25630	210- 244560

Methodology:
HPLC-UV

(Wang et al., 2003)

Samples: Human Serum	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.	30400-307600 (D+L)
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Methodology: RIA

399 N.R.: not reported; N.D.: not determined; D+L is used when the result corresponds to both thyroxine
400 stereoisomers combined; CPBA: Competitive Protein-Binding Analysis; LC-MS/MS: Liquid
401 Chromatography-Tandem Mass Spectrometry; RIA: Radioimmunoassay; HF-LLLME-CE-UV: Hollow Fiber-
402 Three Phases Liquid Microextraction-Capillary Electrophoresis-Ultraviolet Spectroscopy; ICP-MS:
403 Inductively Coupled Plasma-Mass Spectrometry; ECLIA: Electrochemiluminescent Immunoassay; HPLC-
404 UV: High Performance Liquid Chromatography-Ultraviolet Spectroscopy.

405

406 4 Conclusion

407 This study successfully developed and validated a novel analytical method for the
408 extraction and quantification of eight THs, including the chiral forms of thyroxine in HM. By
409 integrating a three-phase hollow-fiber liquid-phase microextraction (HF-LPME) technique with
410 an UHPLC column-switching system, we achieved exceptional sensitivity and reproducibility.
411 Advanced detection techniques, such as QTOF, ICP-MS, and IMMS, facilitated the comprehensive
412 characterization of THs, providing both quantitative data and structural insights. Notably, UHPLC-
413 QTOF enabled the determination of T₀, a form of thyroxine that does not contain iodide.

414 The application of this method to 30 HM samples demonstrated its robustness and
415 reliability in detecting THs at natural levels. These findings mark a significant advancement in the
416 field, offering the first quantitative analysis of chiral T₄. This methodological innovation has the
417 potential to be applied in broader nutritional and clinical studies, enhancing our understanding
418 of the biochemical composition of HM and its critical role in infant development.

419 Future research should aim to expand the applicability of this method by investigating
420 variations in THs concentrations across different populations and stages of lactation.
421 Furthermore, the of certified reference materials specifically designed for the quantification of
422 THs in HM would represent a substantial step forward improving comparability and
423 reproducibility in future studies. Currently, inconsistencies in analytical methods and the
424 absence of standardized materials pose challenges to harmonizing results across investigations.
425 Developing well-characterized reference materials with defined concentrations of THs, including
426 their chiral forms, would facilitate consistent validation and calibration of analytical methods.

427 This work underscores the importance of precise analytical tools in addressing complex
428 biological questions, paving the way for enhanced nutritional and therapeutic strategies in
429 maternal and infant health.

430

431 Appendix A. Supplementary Information

432 Supplementary data includes details about the material and method, results and
433 discussion sections. One supplementary figure and two supplementary tables are included in
434 this file. The Supplementary data is available free of charge at <https://doi.org/>

435

436 **Conflict of Interest**

437 The authors declare no competing financial interest.

438

439 **CRedit author statement**

440 Rafael de Fátima Vélez Pérez: Investigation, data curation, visualization, formal analysis, writing
441 – review and editing.

442 Ana Arias Borrego: supervision, data interpretation, investigation and writing – review and
443 editing.

444 Ines Velasco and Berta Soldevila: Investigation, resources, writing – review and editing.

445 Tamara García Barrera: conceptualization, supervision, data interpretation, investigation,
446 methodology, writing – original draft, funding acquisition, resources, project administration.

447 All authors contributed to the final version of the manuscript.

448 **Declaration of Interest**

449 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interest or personal
450 relationship that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

451

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461 **References**

462 Bode, H. H., Vanjonack, W. J., & Crawford, J. D. (1978). Mitigation of Cretinism by Breast-Feeding.
463 *Pediatrics*, 62(1), 13–16. <https://doi.org/10.1542/PEDS.62.1.13>

464 Chatzimichalakis, P. F., Samanidou, V. F., Verpoorte, R., & Papadoyannis, I. N. (2004).
465 Development of a validated HPLC method for the determination of B-complex vitamins in
466 pharmaceuticals and biological fluids after solid phase extraction. *Journal of Separation
467 Science*, 27(14), 1181–1188. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/jssc.200401858>

468 Cimmino, M., Mion, F., Goglia, F., Minaire, Y., & Géloën, A. (1996). Demonstration of in vivo
469 metabolic effects of 3,5-di-iodothyronine. *Journal of Endocrinology*, 149(2), 319–325.
470 <https://doi.org/10.1677/joe.0.1490319>

471 Cunningham, B. A., Moncur, J. T., Huntington, J. T., & Kinlaw, W. B. (1998). “Spot 14” Protein: A
472 Metabolic Integrator in Normal and Neoplastic Cells. *Thyroid (New York, N.Y.)*, 8(9), 815–
473 825. <https://doi.org/10.1089/thy.1998.8.815>

474 Dorea, J. G. (2002). Selenium and breast-feeding. *British Journal of Nutrition*, 88(5), 443–461.
475 <https://doi.org/DOI: 10.1079/BJN2002692>

- 476 Dror, D. K., & Allen, L. H. (2018). Iodine in Human Milk: A Systematic Review. *Advances in*
477 *Nutrition*, 9, 347S-357S. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1093/advances/nmy020>
- 478 Eisdorfer, I. B., & Post, A. (1967). Method to estimate small amounts of l-triiodothyronine in d-
479 triiodothyronine. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 56(9), 1092–1097.
480 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/jps.2600560908>
- 481 Etling, N., & Gehin-Fouque, F. (1984). Iodinated Compounds and Thyroxine Binding to Albumin
482 in Human Breast Milk. *Pediatric Research*, 18(9), 901–903.
483 <https://doi.org/10.1203/00006450-198409000-00020>
- 484 Etling, N., Padovani, E., Fouque, F., & Tato, L. (1986). First-month variations in total iodine
485 content of human breast milks. *Early Human Development*, 13(1), 81–85.
486 [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-3782\(86\)90101-5](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-3782(86)90101-5)
- 487 Goglia, F. (2005). Biological effects of 3,5-diiodothyronine (T2). *Biochemistry (Moscow)*, 70(2),
488 164–172. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10541-005-0097-0>
- 489 Gübitz, G., & Juffmann, F. (1987). Resolution of the enantiomers of thyroid hormones by high-
490 performance liquid-exchange chromatography using a chemically bonded chiral stationary
491 phase. *Journal of Chromatography A*, 404, 391–393.
492 [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9673\(01\)86882-5](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0021-9673(01)86882-5)
- 493 Horst, C., Rokos, H., & Seitz, H. J. (1989). Rapid stimulation of hepatic oxygen consumption by
494 3,5-di-iodo-l-thyronine. *Biochemical Journal*, 261(3), 945–950.
495 <https://doi.org/10.1042/bj2610945>
- 496 Hulbert, A. J. (2000). Thyroid hormones and their effects: a new perspective. *Biological Reviews*,
497 75(4), 519–631. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-185X.2000.tb00054.x>
- 498 Jackson-Hayes, L., Song, S., Lavrentyev, E. N., Jansen, M. S., Hillgartner, F. B., Tian, L., Wood, P.
499 A., Cook, G. A., & Park, E. A. (2003). A Thyroid Hormone Response Unit Formed between
500 the Promoter and First Intron of the Carnitine Palmitoyltransferase-1 α Gene Mediates the
501 Liver-specific Induction by Thyroid Hormone. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 278(10),
502 7964–7972. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.M211062200>
- 503 Jansson, L., Ivarsson, S., Larsson, I., & Ekman, R. (1983). Tri-iodothyronine and thyroxine in
504 human milk. *Acta Paediatrica*, 72(5), 703–705.
505 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1651-2227.1983.tb09797.x>
- 506 Karimova, S. F., Turakulov, Y. K., Salakhova, N. S., & Gulamova, F. Y. (1983). Content of thyroid
507 hormones in human and animal milk and in cow milk based infant formulas. *Endocrinol*
508 *Exp*, 3–4, 237–242.
- 509 Koidl, J., Hödl, H., Schmid, M. G., Konrad, M., Petschauer, S., Kostner, G. M., & Gübitz, G. (2006).
510 Chiral separation of T3 enantiomers using stereoselective antibodies as a selector in micro-
511 HPLC. *Journal of Biochemical and Biophysical Methods*, 69(1), 33–42.
512 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbbm.2006.03.015>
- 513 Kunisue, T., Eguchi, A., Iwata, H., Tanabe, S., & Kannan, K. (2011). Analysis of Thyroid Hormones
514 in Serum of Baikal Seals and Humans by Liquid Chromatography-Tandem Mass
515 Spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) and Immunoassay Methods: Application of the LC-MS/MS
516 Method to Wildlife Tissues. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 45(23), 10140–10147.
517 <https://doi.org/10.1021/es203002a>

- 518 Lanni, A., Moreno, M., Cioffi, M., & Goglia, F. (1992). Effect of 3,3'-diiodothyronine and 3,5-
519 diiodothyronine on rat liver oxidative capacity. *Molecular and Cellular Endocrinology*,
520 86(3), 143–148. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/0303-7207\(92\)90138-V](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/0303-7207(92)90138-V)
- 521 Lanni, A., Moreno, M., Lombardi, A., De Lange, P., Silvestri, E., Ragni, M., Farina, P., Baccari, G.
522 C., Fallahi, P., Antonelli, A., & Goglia, F. (2005). 3,5-Diiodo-L-thyronine powerfully reduces
523 adiposity in rats by increasing the burning of fats. *The FASEB Journal*, 19(11), 1552–1554.
524 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1096/fj.05-3977fje>
- 525 Lee, J., Adhikari, S., Lee, W., & Yoon, H.-R. (2022). *Development of Ultra High-Performance Liquid*
526 *Chromatography-Tandem Mass Spectrometry Method for Enantiomer Resolution of*
527 *Thyroxine on a Chiral Crown Ether Derived Chiral Stationary Phase.*
528 <https://doi.org/10.21203/RS.3.RS-1957831/V1>
- 529 Lee, M. K., Kumar, A. P., & Lee, Y. I. (2008). Kinetic method for enantiomeric determination of
530 thyroid hormone (d,l-thyroxine) using electrospray ionization tandem mass spectrometry
531 (ESI-MS/MS). *IJMSp*, 272(2–3), 180–186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJMS.2008.02.001>
- 532 Lee, Y., Bang, E., Lee, W., & Na, Y.-C. (2021). Simultaneous enantioselective separation method
533 for thyroid hormones using liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry and its
534 applications. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis*, 196, 113904.
535 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpba.2021.113904>
- 536 Li, P., Hu, B., He, M., & Chen, B. (2014). Ion pair hollow fiber liquid–liquid–liquid microextraction
537 combined with capillary electrophoresis-ultraviolet detection for the determination of
538 thyroid hormones in human serum. *Journal of Chromatography A*, 1356, 23–31.
539 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2014.06.046>
- 540 Li, Z.-M., Albrecht, M., Fromme, H., Schramm, K.-W., & De Angelis, M. (2020). Persistent Organic
541 Pollutants in Human Breast Milk and Associations with Maternal Thyroid Hormone
542 Homeostasis. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 54(2), 1111–1119.
543 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.9b06054>
- 544 Lopez, D., Abisambra Socarrás, J. F., Bedi, M., & Ness, G. C. (2007). Activation of the hepatic LDL
545 receptor promoter by thyroid hormone. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - Molecular*
546 *and Cell Biology of Lipids*, 1771(9), 1216–1225.
547 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbailip.2007.05.001>
- 548 Michalke, B., & Schramel, P. (1999). Iodine speciation in biological samples by capillary
549 electrophoresis - inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry. *Electrophoresis*, 20(12),
550 2547–2553. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1522-
551 2683\(19990801\)20:12<2547::AID-ELPS2547>3.0.CO;2-A](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1522-2683(19990801)20:12<2547::AID-ELPS2547>3.0.CO;2-A)
- 552 Michalke, B., Schramel, P., & Witte, H. (2000). Iodine speciation in human serum by reversed-
553 phase liquid chromatography-ICP-mass spectrometry. *Biological Trace Element Research*,
554 78(1), 81–91. <https://doi.org/10.1385/BTER:78:1-3:81>
- 555 Millan-Alanis, J. M., González-González, J. G., Flores-Rodríguez, A., Singh Ospina, N., Maraka, S.,
556 Moreno-Peña, P. J., Brito, J. P., González-Velázquez, C., & Rodríguez-Gutiérrez, R. (2021).
557 Benefits and Harms of Levothyroxine/L-Triiodothyronine Versus Levothyroxine
558 Monotherapy for Adult Patients with Hypothyroidism: Systematic Review and Meta-
559 Analysis. *Thyroid®*, 31(11), 1613–1625. <https://doi.org/10.1089/thy.2021.0270>
- 560 Mizuta, H., Amino, N., Ichihara, K., Harada, T., Nose, O., Tanizawa, O., & Miyai, K. (1983). Thyroid
561 Hormones in Human Milk and their Influence on Thyroid Function of Breast-Fed Babies.
562 *Pediatric Research*, 17(6), 468–471. <https://doi.org/10.1203/00006450-198306000-00008>

- 563 Ness, G. C., & Lopez, D. (1995). Transcriptional Regulation of Rat Hepatic Low-Density
564 Lipoprotein Receptor and Cholesterol 7 α Hydroxylase by Thyroid Hormone. *Archives of*
565 *Biochemistry and Biophysics*, 323(2), 404–408.
566 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1006/abbi.1995.0061>
- 567 Oppenheimer, J. H., Schwartz, H. L., Lane, J. T., & Thompson, M. P. (1991). Functional
568 relationship of thyroid hormone-induced lipogenesis, lipolysis, and thermogenesis in the
569 rat. *The Journal of Clinical Investigation*, 87(1), 125–132.
570 <https://doi.org/10.1172/JCI114961>
- 571 O'Reilly, I. A. N., & Murphy, M. P. (1992). Treatment of hypothyroid rats with T2 (3,5-di-iodo-l-
572 thyronine) rapidly stimulates respiration in subsequently isolated mitochondria.
573 *Biochemical Society Transactions*, 20(1), 59S-59S. <https://doi.org/10.1042/bst020059s>
- 574 Rayman, M. P. (2000). The importance of selenium to human health. *The Lancet*, 356(9225),
575 233–241. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(00\)02490-9](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(00)02490-9)
- 576 Reinhardt, W., Luster, M., Rudorff, K. H., Heckmann, C., Petrasch, S., Lederbogen, S., Haase, R.,
577 Saller, B., Reiners, C., Reinwein, D., & Mann, K. (1998). Effect of small doses of iodine on
578 thyroid function in patients with Hashimoto's thyroiditis residing in an area of mild iodine
579 deficiency. *European Journal of Endocrinology*, 139(1), 23–28.
580 <https://doi.org/10.1530/eje.0.1390023>
- 581 Robinson, L. M., Sylvester, P. W., Birkenfeld, P., Lang, J. P., & Bull, R. J. (1998). Comparison of the
582 effects of iodine and iodide on thyroid function in humans. *Journal of Toxicology and*
583 *Environmental Health, Part A*, 55(2), 93–106. <https://doi.org/10.1080/009841098158539>
- 584 Rohner, F., Zimmermann, M., Jooste, P., Pandav, C., Caldwell, K., Raghavan, R., & Raiten, D. J.
585 (2014). Biomarkers of Nutrition for Development—Iodine Review. *The Journal of Nutrition*,
586 144(8), 1322S-1342S. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.3945/jn.113.181974>
- 587 Sack, J., Frucht, H., Amado, O., Brisk, M., & Lunenfeld, B. (1979). Breast milk thyroxine and not
588 cow's milk may mitigate and delay the clinical picture of neonatal hypothyroidism. *Acta*
589 *Paediatrica*, 68(S277), 54–56. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1651-2227.1979.tb06192.x>
- 591 Salakhova, N. S., Karimova, S. F., & Kallikorm, A. P. (1980). [Lactation regulation and the content
592 of thyroid hormones in the milk of parturients and components of infant food formulas].
593 *Probl Endokrinol (Mosk)*, 26(3), 21–25.
- 594 Scanu, A., Toth, J., Edelstein, C., Koga, S., & Stiller, E. (1969). Fractionation of human serum high
595 density lipoprotein in urea solutions. Evidence for polypeptide heterogeneity.
596 *Biochemistry*, 8(8), 3309–3316. <https://doi.org/10.1021/bi00836a027>
- 597 Slebodziński, A. B., Nowak, J., Gawecka, H., & Sechman, A. (1986). Thyroid hormones and insulin
598 in milk; a comparative study. *Endocrinol. Exp.*, 20(2–3), 247–255.
- 599 Truchet, S., & Honvo-Houéto, E. (2017). Physiology of milk secretion. *Best Practice & Research*
600 *Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism*, 31(4), 367–384.
601 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.beem.2017.10.008>
- 602 Van Wassenaer, A. G., Stulp, M. R., Valianpour, F., Tamminga, P., Ris Stalpers, C., De Randamie,
603 J. S. E., Van Beusekom, C., & De Vijlder, J. J. M. (2002). The quantity of thyroid hormone in
604 human milk is too low to influence plasma thyroid hormone levels in the very preterm
605 infant. *Clinical Endocrinology*, 56(5), 621–627.
606 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2265.2002.01526.x>

607 Vass, R. A., Kiss, G., Bell, E. F., Miseta, A., Bódis, J., Funke, S., Bokor, S., Molnár, D., Kósa, B., Kiss,
608 A. A., Takács, T., Dombai, F., & Ertl, T. (2022). Thyroxine and Thyroid-Stimulating Hormone
609 in Own Mother's Milk, Donor Milk, and Infant Formula. *Life* 2022, Vol. 12, Page 584, 12(4),
610 584. <https://doi.org/10.3390/LIFE12040584>

611 Wainer, I. W. (1993). The impact of new liquid chromatography chiral stationary phase
612 technology on the study of stereoselective pharmacokinetics. *TrAC Trends in Analytical*
613 *Chemistry*, 12(4), 153–158. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-9936\(93\)87017-](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-9936(93)87017-R)
614 R

615 Wang, R., Jia, Z.-P., Hu, X.-L., Xu, L.-T., Li, Y.-M., & Chen, L.-R. (2003). Determination of serum
616 thyroxine enantiomers in patients by liquid chromatography with a chiral mobile phase.
617 *Journal of Chromatography B*, 785(2), 353–359.
618 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1570-0232\(02\)00959-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1570-0232(02)00959-5)

619 Zhang, Q., Lian, X. L., Chai, X. F., Bai, Y., & Dai, W. X. (2013). [Relationship between maternal milk
620 and serum thyroid hormones in patients with thyroid related diseases]. *Zhongguo Yi Xue*
621 *Ke Xue Yuan Xue Bao. Acta Academiae Medicinae Sinicae*, 35(4), 427–431.
622 <https://doi.org/10.3881/J.ISSN.1000-503X.2013.04.013>

623 Zoeller, R. T., & Rovet, J. (2004). Timing of thyroid hormone action in the developing brain:
624 clinical observations and experimental findings. *Journal of Neuroendocrinology*, 16(10),
625 809–818. <https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1365-2826.2004.01243.X>

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644 **Legend of Figures**

645 Figure 1. 2D Spectrum of THs using IMMS. (A) Separation of T₃ and RT₃ in DT spectrum and (B)
646 no separation of stereoisomers of thyroxine.

647 Figure 2. Superimposed chromatographic gradient and UHPLC-QTOF chromatogram showing
648 the separation of MIT, DIT and T₀ standards at 200 µgL⁻¹ and T₃, RT₃ and T₄ at 2 mgL⁻¹.

649 Figure 3. Chromatograms showing the separation of TH standards, at 1 mgL⁻¹ by (A) HPLC-ICP-
650 MS and (B) UHPLC-QTOF. The insets of Figure B show the magnified sections of the
651 chromatogram for better visualization of T₃, RT₃, D-T₄ and L-T₄.

652 Figure 4. Optimization of the following parameters of HF-LPME: (A) Concentration of acceptor
653 phase, (B) pH, (C) ionic strength, (D) time of extraction, (E) agitation speed and (F) temperature
654 of extraction.

655 Figure 5. Typical chromatogram of thyroid hormones in human milk obtained by HF-LPME
656 followed by UHPLC-QTOF.

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658 **Legend of Tables**

659 Table 1. DTs and CCS values of thyroid hormones obtained experimentally by IMMS.

660 Table 2. Limits of detection and quantification, repeatability and reproducibility for thyroid
661 hormones using UHPLC-QTOF and HPLC-ICP-MS.

662 Table 3. Validation parameters of the proposed method (HF-LPME).

663 Table 4. Concentration of THs in 30 HM samples by HF-LPME followed by UHPLC-QTOF
664 compared with previously reported data of THs.